

Interpretations of meanings in mathematics education and students with disabilities on higher school

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The article is an excerpt from a doctoral research and aims to understand about meanings that students with disabilities attribute to studies in mathematics. It is proposed to discuss concepts of Critical Mathematics Education, with interpretations of experiences of meaning according to the proposals of four concepts: foreground, intentionality, personal meaning and action-image. For this, the data production is composed of semi-structured interview with a higher education student. The results suggest the interpretations that the student attributes to studies in mathematics, relate to the socio-political dimension of education and can be described in terms of the concepts covered, with perceptions that reflect possibilities, impossibilities, priorities and confidence in the future.

Background

In Brazil, concerns directed at the purpose of including students with disabilities in educational systems, start with public policies, which are consequences of conquests of struggles and social movements. Today, the entry and permanence of this group of students at the university, make up some of the challenges that require the development of actions to assist this process, such as discussions that look for to facilitate the academic survival of students. Furthermore, as Skovsmose (2017) clarifies, it's not common that university studies address critical reflections in the socio-political context in mathematics. Therefore, it is important that in higher education, students have the opportunity to reflect the socio-political dimension of Mathematics Education, in order to promote their own engagement in studies.

The data presented in this article is part of a doctoral research (Roncato, 2021), conducted in Brazil, and report concerns with teaching and learning of mathematics. In this context, I investigate the following question: what interpretation of meaning in Mathematics Education are carried out in terms of foreground, intentionality, personal meaning and action-image? Understanding student's interpretations about studies in mathematics can reveal social and cultural aspects of learning and teaching, bringing contributions to debates in Critical Mathematics Education.

To start our studies, were invited nine students with disabilities, who were studying in Higher Education. The only requirement in relation to the course they attended was that there be mathematics classes in the curriculum. They are, therefore, students with various disabilities who take varied courses, as shown in the table below:

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Name	Disability	Course
Carolina	Robinow Syndrome	Pedagogy
Júlia	Fragile X Syndrome	Human Resources
Manuela	Fragile X Syndrome	Human Resources
Flor	Auditory processing disorder	Pedagogy
Bela So	Attention deficit disorder	Pedagogy
Polly	Deafness	Brazilian Sign Language
Lívy	Cerebral Palsy	Psychology
Lary	Low Vision	Psychology
Juba	Cerebral Palsy	Radio, Television, Internet

Table 1: The Students

Defining the participants, it was the moment to elaborate the questions that would be realized. In Skovsmose (2014a), Vollstedt (2011) and Kollosche (2017), the necessary and comfortable inspiration was found to start the discussions. The intention was to offer guests moments of reflection on the presence of mathematics in their lives, in dialogues about the topics: *stories of my life; mathematics in my life; mathematics studied in higher education; mathematics in my future.*

The interviews were divided into two moments: the first with the completion of the inquiries and, in the second, the presentation to the participants of the transcription of the results. For the inquiries, different forms of interaction were used, composed of: use of figures, photographs, sounds, clippings from newspapers and magazines, various objects, words or phrases and images of tasks of mathematics referring to the mathematical contents studied by them. These strategies had the objective to promoting accessibility and benefit communication. For example, were presented for the participants with a variation of figures, objects and photographs of animals¹. Then they should choose ones that best represented what they thought and felt about mathematics (Figure 1):

Figure 1: Mathematics in my life. (Created by author)

This strategy model worked as an element that triggered the discussions, expanding the conversations that, in an interview in a questionnaire format, might not have the same effect.

For the analysis, we sought to transcribe the data according to the moments that indicated the experiences of meanings in Mathematics Education, interpreted according to four

¹ David Kollosche in his research uses this idea relating mathematical feelings to an animal. For more information see Kollosche (2017).

concepts: foreground, intentionality, personal meaning and action-image. This is because there are suspicions that these concepts may influence student engagement in mathematics studies, constituting some possibilities for interpretations of meanings. With Ole Skovsmose, we sought the understandings of foreground and intentionality; Maike Vollstedt contributed the concept of personal meaning; as for the concept of image-action, it was built from the understandings of self-concept, auto-exclusion and microexclusion.

Dialogues with the four concepts

Skovsmose (2014b) identifies in Mathematics Education concerns in face of a variety of conditions in which the teaching and learning of mathematics occur. It is based on dialogue and involves notions such as, for example, autonomy, freedom and social justice. Of these concerns, we can mention the concepts, such as: foreground, inclusion, landscapes of investigation, matemacy, mathematics in action, representativeness, meaning, intentionality, among others.

Thus, it is important to discuss the context in which students' learning occurs, understanding that some of them may recognize that studies in mathematics are fundamental for their professional future; others may only intend to achieve good exam results; and, still, there are those who are not interested in mathematics, because they are not engaged in the execution of the tasks of this discipline. In this case, Skovsmose (2018, p. 766) argues that "when students do not realize the meaning of what they are doing in the mathematics classroom, it may be due to the fact that they cannot connect it to the future". The author, then, proposes that the basis for the construction of interpretations of meaning in Mathematics Education, is the engagement of students in the context of the mathematics classroom and suggests, even though giving interpretations of meaning "through a foreground can reveal a socio-political formation of students' meaning experiences" (p. 766).

According to the purposes of Skovsmose (2014a), foreground is a process directed to the future of the person (or group of people), considering several aspects, such as: the possibilities that the political, social and economic situations provide for the person; what she, in these situations, considers possible to achieve; realities or illusions, hopes and dream conquests. For this reason, it is not static and can be reworked. And it represents aspirations and desires, defeats or achievements. It doesn't mean getting to a certain place in the future, but recognizing that you can get there. In addition, the author understands that foregrounds are multiple and built according to individual or group experiences.

As for intentionality, Skovsmose (2014a) suggests a reinterpretation of the concept, including social structures, with economic, political, cultural and discursive factors, understanding, therefore, that when addressing the interpretation of a student's intentionality when the focus is on studies, it is important to consider the social, his/her real life. Intentionality is to be directed to the choice of a student to perform or not perform the mathematical tasks proposed by the teacher, for example; also has to do with the reason, decision in this execution: perhaps the student decides positively to recognize in the learning of this content, an important element in the composition your professional future; or maybe he likes math and wants to improve his school performance, achieving good results in exams.

Thus, the intentionality to carry out school tasks or not, is conditioned to the student's commitment to learn this or that mathematical content. If the discussions focus on the school environment, a student's priorities tend to reveal the reasons that drive him or her away from studies, his intentionality when dealing with mathematics studies. The personal meaning that the student attributes to studies in mathematics

Vollstedt (2011) conceptualizes personal meaning as being subjective, expressiveness, object and action when the focus is on the student's mathematical learning. For her, a mathematical content is understood by the student if it is admitted as relevant personally. In this case, the study of the construction of personal meaning is important, since it can reveal potentialities and affinities evidenced by students with respect to mathematical studies, the relevance for each one in engaging with learning situations. It can be rebuilt according to each person's school and social life experiences. Thus, personal meaning is linked to the relevance that disciplinary contexts and tasks have for the student.

We can understand that personal meaning is linked to classroom situations in the moments when these contents and tasks are presented, to the experiences previously experienced when the focus is on learning, on the expectations of each one, has to do with intentionality and with the foreground. I also admit a relationship with the student's image of himself, bringing him closer to or away from his studies.

The authors Alrø and Skovsmose (2004), when proposing learning as action, open discussions conceptualizing zooming-in and zooming-out, understanding the former as the approach of students in learning, which develops from their engagement in tasks, intentionality of them. For the second case, students not engagement themselves in tasks, they drive away, the decision is not focused on studying or learning.

From this conceptualization, there are several elements that interfere in the engagement with the studies. One of them may be a student's image of himself. By image I understand how the perception that instigates, that pushes forward towards studies; or that drive the students away, repudiating everything that concerns mathematics. This image can be positive (it instigates, pushes for studies), it can be negative (it repudiates, it drives away) and it can be reconstructed in face of the possibilities and opportunities in face of a certain circumstance. The action-image concept is built from the influence of other concepts: microexclusion, self-concept and auto-exclusion. Carneiro, Martinelli and Sisto (2003, p. 428) present comparisons between students' difficulties directed to learning and self-concept, admitting that: "self-concept has been pointed out as one of the influencers in this process", as the student experiences successful experiences or school failure, according to the curricular component. In other words, a student may have a bad self-concept for one discipline and a good one for another.

Self-concept is the idea that the person makes of himself, a construct that influences self-esteem and that in some cases, becomes an obstacle when the context is turned to studies. We can understand how the student's image of himself, which can move him, both moving him away and bringing him closer to his studies.

The distancing of students in mathematics, the exclusion that many students impose, is conceptualized by Kollosche (2017) as auto-exclusion from mathematics, thus defining: “auto-exclusion from mathematics education can be conceptualized as the exclusion from the mathematical discourse by the learner” (p. 38). Therefore, Kollosche clarifies that auto-exclusion “is not merely the result of psychological dispositions of the individual, which could then be changed by pedagogical intervention, but that self-exclusion is created in the interplay of the individual and the social environment” (p. 39). For the understanding of microexclusions, Faustino et al. (2018, p. 900) clarify that “microexclusions are subtle practices, carried out consciously or not, which tend to isolate the individual in a given environment”. If a student cannot keep up with the learning pace of other colleagues, he can isolate himself; or even when he feels inferior and afraid of his colleagues in the face of a lack of understanding of disciplinary tasks.

I consider that microexclusions, self-concept and auto-exclusion tend to interfere with the student’s image of himself, when the focus is on studies in mathematics. If this image is negative, intentionality may not be directed towards engagement in studies, distancing the student from learning; if, on the contrary, the image is positive, it can promote a movement of approach, one directed towards learning.

Thus, what moves the student towards mathematical studies (or repels), his willingness to act in relation to these studies, energy, the possibility of boosting his own learning, performance, has to do with the image that it makes itself that directed to these mathematical studies. Action is an active part of learning, it is enthusiasm, the energy that acts on the student, moving him to studies. Therefore, it is possible to explore the interpretations of personal meaning in view of the student’s image of himself, of the foreground, of intentionality. In addition, Skovsmose (2017, p. 18) asks “what could Critical Mathematics Education mean for different groups of students?”, including students with disabilities. The challenge, then, is to propose advances in Critical Mathematical Education, dialoguing with interpretations of meaning, in the possible encounters of the four concepts.

For the article, the reports of a participant in the study, the relations that she establishes between the mathematics studied in higher education, professional practice and life itself are presented.

I’m afraid of math, I’m afraid of spiders

The way the person interprets the possibilities and impossibilities, joys and frustrations, opportunities, obstacles, hopes and fears, has to do with the experiences already lived and the influence of factors such as social, economic, political and cultural. In this sense, Skovsmose (2014a) relates the notion of foreground to the way in which the person experiences the experiences around him. So, knowing childhood, family aspects, cultural background and some detail of the life of people, can reveal tendencies to the foreground that, according to purpose Skovsmose (2014a), “the person’s background it refers to everything she has ever lived, while the foreground refers to everything that may happen to her” (p. 35).

Who is Julia?

Júlia is student and at the time of the interview she was studying Human Resources. She reported that she had a happy childhood, surrounded by friends and games. Now, if there are any conversation related to mathematics in matters between friends, she considers that the conversation will be difficult to continue. She adds that she is afraid of mathematics, with its giant numbers and formulas:

Student: Mathematics is something I don't get along with very well [...], I find it difficult to understand [...] mathematical operation, giant numbers, formulas.

Then, the student compared mathematics with the feelings she has for the spiders:

Student: I am terrified of the spider, the spider has several legs that remind me of mathematics, with various accounts.

It is observed in Julia's words, a certain fear and detachment from everything related to mathematics, since she admits to be a discipline that is difficult to understand, having difficulties in expressing a positive relationship with this knowledge in higher education.

Student: At university I never liked it. But it was not always so. At school things were easier and I felt better, because I could understand, easier.

When Julia saw on the table some math tasks, she was learning in her university classes, she frowned in an expression of disliking, as if to exclude herself, admitting that the content was too difficult for her, that she did not understand. And she completed by making references to the sad moments experienced in classes, pointing out that she was humiliated by colleagues in the face of the difficulties she had in carrying out the tasks. Such an attitude can lead the student to move away from studies, promoting a negative image of himself/herself when it comes to engaging in tasks:

Student: For me, mathematics is something impossible to understand, very complicated and leaves me in a somewhat lost situation.

The image that the person makes of himself (or herself) is a construct that influences self-esteem, becoming, in some cases, an obstacle if that image for negative and, at other times, when positive, instigates, pushes towards something. In this case, Júlia considers that mathematics for her is something difficult to understand and that leaves her isolated, "half lost", perhaps an obstacle that makes it difficult to arrive somewhere in the future.

According to the understanding of Skovsmose (2014a), foreground is related to several aspects, among them, realities, illusions, hopes, possibilities or impossibilities. When asked about her wishes and expectations for the future, possible achievements, the student said she wants to have autonomy in life, be financially independent, have a good job and admitted that mathematics will be present in this future, only in ordinary financial operations, like shopping at the supermarket.

However, faced with the impossibilities of understanding mathematics, Júlia opted for alternatives, composing a new future that would make her happy. So, days after the interview, at our new meeting, Júlia said she had given up on the Human Resources course because, according to her, the course was permeated by "a lot of mathematics with giant numbers".

It appeared that her decision revolved around social influences and the promotion of the moment she was in. Thus, the student re-elaborated possibilities towards the future, then finding a reason to direct her to tomorrow: she opted for another course. This establishment of new possibilities for the future opened some paths for her, finding the reasons that lead to studies, a new intentionality. Given this context, Júlia invited me to participate in a research about Fashion (the new course she was studying). From the answers to the questions, the task that she should perform involves mathematical elements, with data collection, construction and interpretation of graphs and tables.

Although at the beginning of the study, Julia demonstrated a departure from mathematics, now, in the reworking of her future, she confessed that mathematics seems simpler to her, demonstrating that she likes it: “but this math is cool, without the giant numbers”. She seems satisfied and happy in the face of the new learning in mathematics that were now available.

Skovsmose (2014a) is attentive to the existence of a close relationship between intentionality and foreground. The reasons that lead Julia to the new studies indicate a directionality, a being directed towards, an intentionality and, in this case, it concerns her foreground. The situation that drives her is guided by intentions, priorities, motives. According to purpose Skovsmose et al. (2009, p. 238), “the meaning of mathematical education is not only linked to the understanding of mathematical concepts, but also to the foreground of students and is related to the intentions for learning”, with the reasons, with the affinities and, therefore, point to learning.

In addition, for Vollstedt (2011) it is essential to understand the universe that surrounds the student and the personal relevance that the studies have for him (or her), revealing potential and affinities that are evidenced by the students with regard to mathematical studies, being reconstructed according to the interpretations of each person’s school and social life experiences. Possibly a reason, an intentionality in contact with knowledge, an engagement directed to learning. For Júlia, the re-elaboration of the reasons that propel her to studies may also reveal a re-elaboration of the personal meaning directed to mathematics studies.

Some discussions

Now, I want to present my views on interpretations of meaning in terms of these four concepts: foreground, intentionality, personal meaning and action-image.

On our first meeting, Julia showed a real aversion to everything that contained mathematics. Several times she cited the math of accounts, giant numbers and formulas, even comparing it with the dread she feels for spiders. As she herself stated, she never liked mathematics at the university, proposing that it was not relevant to the study. Still, she recognized the possibility of using mathematics in ordinary financial transactions, such as grocery shopping. The presence of mathematics is summarized in quantifications and numbers, in additions and other mathematical operations. There are suspicions that the image of herself takes her away from her studies. She dropped out of the Human Resources course, justifying that it contained a lot of math and giant numbers, demonstrating fears and obstacles, an irrelevant study.

It turns out that foreground is not static and can be reworked, as well as the choices we make throughout life, which can change. Júlia changed, having new priorities and, in this journey, took possession of cultural, social and economic factors from the moment that was revealed before her, in other direction to a new course. Intentionality can be reorganized, under the influence of various aspects, such as opportunities, desires, hopes, expectations and possibilities for the future. In the new studies, Júlia takes mathematics classes, but, as she said, it is a good mathematics and, therefore, she reorganizes her intentionality by addressing the possibilities of achievements. Apparently, the new studies are providing greater involvement of Julia in the educational situation, favouring her engagement in the mathematical context. This fact also contributed to her reconstructing personal meaning, highlighting the relevance of mathematics for new professional achievements. Still, when she declared that this mathematics was good, there are signs of an approximation with the studies, with the action-image being reinterpreted by approximation in the face of the change of reference.

More reflections

In this article, I proposed discussions seeking to understand what meanings a student with a disability who is studying higher education attributes to studies in mathematics. The paths taken were determined considering what I admit as one of the fundamental factors to reflect on mathematical learning, with interpretations of meanings attributed to the studies. My inquiries were guided by an understanding of the four concepts: foreground, intentionality, personal meaning and action-image.

I also follow Skovsmose's arguments (2018, p. 766) when admitting that "students' experiences of meaning have to do with how they see their future opportunities in life". In this case, the author proposes that the meaning is, first of all, an experience and highlights that "when students do not realize the meaning of what they are doing in the mathematics classroom, it may be due to the fact that they cannot connect it. you to the future" (p. 769).

Resuming Skovsmose's (2018) understandings, it seems that Julia did not understand the meaning of what she was doing in math classes when she was studding at the first course. At the first moment of the interview, Júlia admitted that there was no connection between the mathematics studied and the future. However, from the moment that she seeks other expectations for the future, there are signs of optimism and confidence in herself directed towards studies. The data suggest that the interpretations of the meaning experiences with students with disabilities attribute to studies, relate to the socio-political dimension and can be described in terms of foreground, intentionality, personal meaning and image-action.

Then, for Júlia, the experiences of meaning can be interpreted connecting to the proposals of the four concepts: Foreground as it is reworked and linked to the expectations of professional and personal life; Intentionality, as reorganized with reference to the professional future; Personal Meaning, as reconstructed for relevant to new studies; action-image, which is reinterpreted as an approximation to the new study references. It is possible that Júlia found reasons for studying mathematics, from socio-political influence in her life.

In Skovsmose (2018), the author approximates the concepts of foreground and intentionality, when it is including sociopolitical contexts in interpretations of meaning, when the focus is on studies in mathematics. Thus, I understand that these interpretations relate to the way the student perceives the possibilities, opportunities, longings, expectations, hopes, obstacles, aims, decision, motive, joys or sorrows related to the future. It is related to priorities that studies have for the student, can reveal affinities and potentials, the personal meaning. The student's image of herself or himself, directing him or her intention to the learning process, also receives sociopolitical influences. As a consequence, I consider the four concepts (foreground, intentionality, personal meaning and action-image), can connecting with each other in the student's learning experiences. I don't mean to say that this is the only path, motive, purpose towards learning, but it is one of the.

References

- Alrø, H., & Skovsmose, O. (2004). *Dialogue and learning in mathematics education: Intention, reflection, critique*. Boston: Kluwer.
- Carneiro, G. R. S., Martinelli, S. C., & Sisto, F. F. (2003). Autoconceito e dificuldades de aprendizagem na escrita. *Psicologia: Reflexão e Crítica*, 16(3), 427–434. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0102-79722003000300002>
- Faustino, A. C., Moura, A. Q., Silva, G. H. G., Muzzinati, J. L., & Skovsmose, O. (2018). Macroinclusão e microexclusão no contexto educacional. *Revista Eletrônica de Educação*, 12(3), 898–911.
- Kollosche, D. (2017). Auto-exclusion in mathematics education. *Revista Paranaense de Educação Matemática*, 6(12), 38–63.
- Roncato, C. (2021). *Significado em educação matemática e estudantes com deficiência: possibilidades de encontros de conceitos* (Doctoral dissertation). Universidade Estadual Paulista “Júlio de Mesquita Filho”, Rio Claro, Brazil.
- Skovsmose, O., Alrø, H., Valero, P., & Scanduzzi, P. P. (2009). Antes de dividir temos que somar: Entrevistando foregrounds de estudantes indígenas. *BOLEMA: Boletim de Educação Matemática*, 22(34), 237–262.
- Skovsmose, O. (2014b). *Um convite à educação matemática crítica*. Campinas, SP: Papirus.
- Skovsmose, O. (2018). Interpretações de significados em educação matemática. *BOLEMA: Boletim de Educação Matemática*, 32(62), 764–780.
- Skovsmose, O. (2014a). *Foregrounds: Opaque stories about learning*. Sense.
- Skovsmose, O. (2017). O que poderia significar a educação matemática crítica para diferentes grupos de estudantes? *Revista Paranaense de Educação Matemática*, 6(12), 18–37.
- Vollstedt, M. (2011). *Sinnkonstruktion und Mathematiklernen in Deutschland und Hong Kong: Eine rekonstruktiv-empirisch Studie*. Wiesbaden, Germany: Vieweg + Teubner.